

ISic3599

I.Sicily inscription 3599

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

stone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

reused in walls of a farm of the C18, north of Modica

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Modica, eused in walls of a farm of the C18, north of Modica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491434

EDCS 46600165

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0677

Sammito, A.M., Rizzone, V.G. 2007. Aspetti della cristianizzazione negli Ibeli sud-orientali. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E.(eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra*

tardoantico e altomedioevo. Palermo. pp. 1613-1646. At 1623-1624 tav.9.6

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